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Benedicamus Domino: delight in singing praise to God at Las Huelgas of Burgos

IN the first half of the 13th century, the Archbishop of Toledo, Rodrigo Ximénez de Rada (d.1247), portrayed the royal nunnery of Las Huelgas near Burgos (Castile, Spain) as a site of overflowing wealth and visual delights, where the constant presence of servants ensured that the nuns had no task other than ‘taking pleasure’ (*delectantur*) in singing praise to God.¹ While Las Huelgas was founded in the 1180s as a Cistercian house, and soon after the status of special daughter of Cîteaux was bestowed on it, far from conforming to the Cistercian ascetic ideal, Las Huelgas actually functioned as a sort of palatine house with a focus on prayer that retained many of the sensorial pleasures and comforts customarily associated with courtly life.² Not surprisingly, while royal and papal protection supported the continuity of the community’s special customs, relations between Las Huelgas and the Cistercian Order went through periods of serious conflict during the late Middle Ages.³

The ambivalent relationship between Las Huelgas and the Cistercian Order is clearly reflected in the liturgical practices of the Castilian nunnery. While the main structure and organization of the liturgy at Las Huelgas followed the prescriptions given in Cistercian customaries, the community of nuns adorned the Divine Office and the cloister processions with a variety of indulgent pleasures: the sight of secular architectural decorations, the touch of luxurious textiles or the sound of delightful music.⁴ Such musical delights included complex polyphony, liturgical tropes and virtuoso monophonic singing—all practices explicitly forbidden by the Cistercian Order. The 14th-century manuscript known as the Las Huelgas Codex (Burgos, Biblioteca

del Monasterio de Las Huelgas, Ms. 11; hereafter *Hu*) contains the repertory of polyphonic Mass Ordinary settings, sequences, organa, conductus and motets that was in use at the royal nunnery during the 13th and 14th centuries.⁵ Within this repertory, the settings of the *Benedicamus Domino* occupy a prominent place, accounting for more than a fifth of the pieces in the book. *Benedicamus Domino* is moreover the only versicle of the Divine Office that is set polyphonically in *Hu*.⁶

This article uses the repertory of the *Benedicamus Domino* in *Hu* as a lens through which to examine the richness and complexity of the celebration of the Divine Office at Las Huelgas of Burgos. It offers a general overview of music for the *Benedicamus*, exploring its ritual function within the Office liturgy and scrutinizing the available evidence for the singers involved in its performance. The analysis of this particular versicle and its various musical instantiations illuminates the broader social and political contexts of the liturgy as performed at Las Huelgas during the late Middle Ages.

The *Benedicamus* repertory in *Hu*

Hu contains *Benedicamus* tropes for the most important celebrations throughout the liturgical year (Nativity, Paschal time, Marian feasts and major saints such as St John the Baptist) as well as a number of untroped polyphonic settings that could be performed or even adapted for use on multiple different occasions. *Hu* transmits a total of 38 *Benedicamus*-related pieces, including motets. This number stands out, especially in comparison with the number of Ordinary Mass movement settings in the same manuscript: five of the Kyrie, one of the

Gloria, one of the Credo, eight of the Sanctus and five of the Agnus Dei. In terms of liturgical compositions, only the 33 Sequences in *Hu* rival the number of *Benedicamus* settings.⁷ It is therefore impossible to discuss all of the *Benedicamus* settings in detail here. Nonetheless, this article offers a close reading of several examples, selected to illustrate both the stylistic diversity of this repertory as well as the creative processes involved in its compilation.

Throughout the Middle Ages and across Europe, the performance of *Benedicamus* plainchant melodies retained a very flexible character, often relying on unwritten practices, as Anne Walters Robertson has noted.⁸ *Benedicamus* chants frequently borrowed pre-existing material from Kyrie and responsory melodies. The repertory of *Benedicamus Domino* transmitted in *Hu* perfectly illustrates this culture of musical reworking and adaptation. While most of the polyphonic music transmitted in *Hu* is known from other earlier sources—such as the Parisian manuscripts Florence, Biblioteca Medicea-Laurenziana, Pluteo 29.1 (hereafter *F*) and Montpellier, Bibliothèque Interuniversitaire, Séction de Médecine, H 196—several of the numerous settings of the *Benedicamus Domino* in *Hu* are unique pieces that reflect an apparently local practice. Closer inspection reveals, however, that most of these ‘unique’ *Benedicamus* settings were created by borrowing and reworking musical material from other sections of the manuscript.

One of the most striking examples of this is found in the untroped *Benedicamus* on fols.24v–25r. While the setting is unique in this form, it combines musical material from three different pieces (see *illus.1*).⁹ The starting melisma is taken from the polyphonic responsory *Iudea et Iherusalem*.¹⁰ The *Domino* passage is taken from the motet *Dum superbit / Tenura* (*Hu*, fols.83r–84v, *unicum*), and the concluding *punctus organicus* is the same as that for the *Ave Maria* (*Hu*, fols.151v–152v, *unicum*).¹¹

The *Benedicamus Domino* is the only liturgical item that was supplied with florid organa in *Hu*, yet in most of these pieces, organal flourishes do not ornament plainchant melodies, but are rather set over single tones that functioned as drone-like passages. These *puncta organica* could be added at the beginning, within or at the end of existing settings, as desired, and presumably this could have

been an unwritten practice which extended beyond the notated examples found in *Hu*. For instance, the troped *Benedicamus Verbum Patris* (Nativity), copied on fol.25r, presents a polyphonic texture typical of the note-against-note discant of a conductus. However, the same piece is copied again on fols.26v–27r in an extended version, in which extended organal flourishes over long-held tenor notes are interpolated between the verses of the poetic trope (see *ex.1*).

The *Benedicamus Hec est mater* (fol.27r) presents a musical structure very similar to the extended version of the *Verbum Patris*. Although no shorter version of *Hec est mater* has been preserved in *Hu*, we could speculate whether, here too, the organal passages (or *puncta organica*) were inserted between the trope verses of a pre-existing piece in conductus style. Possibly, therefore, *Hec est mater* was also sung in a compressed, simpler and less melismatic version that did not need to be committed to writing, since its organal melismas could simply have been excised as necessary from the more elaborate version of the piece recorded in *Hu*. While the tenor of the opening *punctus organicus* is rhythmized (with repeated notes) in the same trochaic patterns as the upper voice (see *illus.2*), the number of statements of the tenor’s rhythmic pattern of repeated notes does not coincide precisely with the upper voice: it seems that the scribe notated several but not all of the iterations of the tenor’s rhythmic pattern, presuming that this could be extended as necessary and implying a sort of *et cetera*. Furthermore, while the upper voice of the second *punctus organicus* contains very similar figures to that of the opening one, the tenor’s rhythm is not even notated. This seems to suggest that the rhythmicization of such drone-like tenors, with multiple rhythmicized iterations prolonging a single pitch, was an extended, unwritten performance practice, and that the same principle could be applied to other examples transmitted in *Hu*, such as *Benedicamus Verbum Patris*, discussed above.

The two-part *Benedicamus* organum copied on fol.32v offers an eloquent example of the flexible treatment of liturgical melodies in polyphonic *Benedicamus* settings. Originally an organum in which a florid upper voice embellished an underlying *Benedicamus* plainchant (as attested by the concordance in *F*), this piece lost its original tenor line

Resp. *Iudea et Iherusalem*
(*F*, fol.65r; *W*₁, fol.17r; *W*₂, fol.47r)

Motet *Dum superbit / Tenura*
(*Hu*, fols.83r–84v, *unicum*)

Conductus *Ave Maria*
(concluding *punctus organicus*,
Hu, fols.151r–152v, *unicum*)

1 *Benedicamus Domino* in *Hu*, fols.24v–25r (© Patrimonio Nacional)

at some point in transmission into *Hu*. The tenor was here replaced with a freely invented one bearing no resemblance to any *Benedicamus* or other plainchant melody.¹² Example 2 shows a comparison of this *Benedicamus* in *Hu* with its concordance in manuscript *F*.¹³ The accident is difficult to explain.

Perhaps the piece was transmitted from memory by a singer who could only remember or cared only to record the florid upper part. Alternatively, a written exemplar for the piece could have been damaged, or simply have been left incomplete, possibly because it was taken for granted that a scribe would know

Ex.1 *Benedicamus Verbum Patris* in *Hu*, fols.25r and 26v–27r. Adapted from Asensio's edition.

simpler version
on fol.25r

1. Ver - bum Pa - tris ho - di - e pro - ces - sit ex Vir -
2. Pa - cem bo - nis om - ni - bus nun - ci - a - vit an -

1. Ver - bum Pa - tris ho - di - e pro - ces - sit ex Vir -
2. Pa - cem bo - nis om - ni - bus nun - ci - a - vit an -

organal
interpolations
on fol.26v

gi - ne vir - tu - tes an - ge - li - - ce. Cum ca -
ge - lus. Re - ful - sit pa - sto - ri - - bus ve - ri

gi - ne vir - tu - tes an - ge - li - - ce. Cum ca -
ge - lus. Re - ful - sit pa - sto - ri - - bus ve - ri

no - ro iu - bi - lo, Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no.
so - lis cla - ri - tas. De - o di - ca - mus gra - ci - as.

no - ro iu - bi - lo, Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no.
so - lis cla - ri - tas. De - o di - ca - mus gra - ci - as.

and be able to supply the appropriate *Benedicamus* chant. It seems that the text ‘Benedicamus Domino alleluia alleluia’ must have been present in any exemplar, since this text is (correctly) supplied in *Hu* despite the lack of its accompanying chant melody. Nevertheless, the scribe either did not know or have to hand the appropriate chant tenor, or made a deliberate choice to supply a new one. Whatever the

reason, the provision of an artificial *Benedicamus* tenor suggests that polyphonic textures could be understood as part of a principally decorative musical sound and effect, and one that was not necessarily dependent on any association with a pre-existent liturgical melody.

Most pieces in *Hu* that borrow actual plainchant melodies are not florid organa, but have the discant

2 *Benedicamus Hec est Mater* in *Hu*, fol.27r (© Patrimonio Nacional)

texture and rhythmical treatment characteristic of the 13th-century conductus. This is the case to such an extent that it is hard to distinguish stylistically the *Benedicamus* settings that borrow liturgical melodies from those which are entirely newly composed in conductus style, such as the three-part *Benedicamus Resurgentis Domini* on fol.28r (*unicum*). *Hu* also includes less complex *Benedicamus* settings that are clearly not based on plainchant melodies. These include imitative canons that are easy to memorize and perform, even by non-experts in polyphonic singing.¹⁴ Examples of this kind are also known from other nunneries, where these pieces appear isolated in the context of plainchant manuscripts.¹⁵

Another classic example of borrowing practices involved in the performance of the *Benedicamus* is the retexting of Kyrie melodies with the words *Benedicamus Domino*. This was a common—and, it seems, often unwritten—practice in the Middle Ages of which *Hu* preserves various concrete examples. The untroped polyphonic *Benedicamus* setting on fol.30r is simply a retexting of the two-part Kyrie *Rex virginum* (fol.1r), which is in turn based on the melody of the Kyrie *Cunctipotens genitor*.¹⁶ The untroped polyphonic *Benedicamus* setting on fol.22v is also based on a Kyrie melody (Kyrie *Conditor alme*).

The creation of new *Benedicamus* tropes at Las Huelgas also involved the borrowing of texts and melodies from sequences. For instance, the

text of the monophonic *Benedicamus Sane per omnia*, added by a secondary scribe on fol.160v, was drawn from strophes 5a and b of the sequence *De Christi corpore* on fols.71v–73v, while its music was adapted from the lower voice of the three-part *Benedicamus* trope *Resurgentis Domini* on fols.28r–29v (*unicum*).¹⁷ A different musical setting for the same text—*Sane per omnia*—is found on fol.165v. Similarly, the text of the *Benedicamus O quam pretiosum*, added by yet another scribe on fol.164r, is taken from strophe 9 of the sequence *Helizabeth Zacarie* on fols.63r–64v, while its music was adapted from strophe 2 of the sequence *Eterni numinis* on fol.38v–40r (= *De Christi corpore*, fols.71v–73v).¹⁸ And a different musical setting for the same text—*O quam pretiosum*—is also found on fol.156v.

In addition to the somewhat ad hoc creation of monophonic *Benedicamus* tropes through the repurposing of pre-existing sequences, *Hu* also contains more complex polyphonic settings of the *Benedicamus Domino* in the form of motets. The motet fascicle of *Hu* opens with three consecutive *Benedicamus* motets, and another four are based on pre-existing clausulae settings of the *Domino* sections of *Benedicamus Domino* plainchants. Perhaps the best known *Benedicamus* motet in *Hu* is *Clastrum* [i.e. *Castrum*] *puđici[ci]e / Virgo viget melius / Flos filius* (fol.116r), based on the famous *Benedicamus* melody *Flos filius*, and with multiple musical concordances with different texts for the *duplum* and *triplum*.¹⁹ In *Hu*, the *duplum* text

Ex.2 *Benedicamus Domino* in *Hu*, fol.32v, and *F*, fol.88r

Be - ne - di - ca - mus do - mi - no. Al - le - lu - ya

- [lu]-yia. A[l-l]e - Al - le -

[different melody from here on]

[...]

ends with the words ‘Benedicamus Domino’, which makes it function as a *Benedicamus* trope polyphonically juxtaposed on a textless *Benedicamus* melody. The motet *Virgo parit puerum / Nova salus hominis* / [*Benedicamus Domino*] on fol.99v (*unicum*) shows a similar construction, but with an even

greater effect, as the words ‘Benedicamus Domino’ are declaimed by the two upper voices simultaneously at the motet’s conclusion. The tenor of this motet is taken from a *Benedicamus* melody for the solemn Vespers found in the *Intonarrium toletanum*, from Toledo Cathedral.²⁰

The upper parts of the four-voice monotextual motet *Belial vocatur / Tenura* (fol.82r, *unicum*) also close with the words ‘Benedicamus Domino’. The tenor line of this motet, however, has not been identified as a liturgical melody. Nicolas Bell has noted that the emendation ‘necatur’ (for ‘vocatur’) is all that is necessary to make the text an acrostic on the words ‘Benedicamus Domino’, initially using the first two letters of each word of the upper-voice text and then, repeated, using the first letter only.²¹

Belial vocatur [i.e. **n**ecatur]
diffusa cal[[i]ditas,
muse dominator
militantis novitas.
Benedictus exitus
nesciens errorem,
decorus introitus
conferens amorem.
Mensus ulnis Simeonis
dominator omnium,
miratur infusionis
natura officium.
O Benedicamus Domino

This remarkable composition—whose use of an acrostic is otherwise unprecedented in the context of *Ars Antiqua*-style compositions—shows how important the *Benedicamus Domino* was in shaping the conception of the motet from the outset.

Finally, it is worth noting that five monophonic *Benedicamus* tropes are the only pieces in *Hu* transmitted in *Ars Nova* notation, a testament to the longevity of interest in this versicle.²² These are the very last additions on spare pages at the end of the codex, copied by various hands possibly in the late 1340s or 1350s. While minim stems were occasionally used by the main scribe of the codex and other secondary scribes working in the 1340s, these scribes largely copied, reworked or borrowed from 12th- and 13th-century materials. In contrast, the last *Benedicamus* additions show the rhythmic patterns characteristic of early *Ars Nova* practice, as described in theoretical treatises from c.1320–50.²³ This makes the *Benedicamus Domino* the liturgical item with the widest stylistic and chronological range across the entire codex *Hu*, including repertoires

and practices originating in the 12th century and spanning through to the mid 14th.

Ritual context

We may wonder why the two words of the simple versicle *Benedicamus Domino*, ‘Let us bless the Lord’, inspired so much creative effort, both musical and poetic. The versicle (and its response) was used so often in religious daily life, that it risked becoming a mere routine phrase. Each morning, the members of the community were awakened individually by one member who knocked the door and declaimed ‘Benedicamus Domino’: the response ‘Deo gratias’ indicated that the individual was awake.²⁴ The same words were used as the concluding sentence after a meal, and closed many orations and prayers throughout the day. In a way, the versicle represented the very essence of monastic life. While it was frequently only spoken or recited in simple tones, the versicle’s profound spiritual and theological implications were actualized in more lengthy performances and rituals within the liturgy of the Divine Office. These extended chants and rituals gave the community an opportunity to meditate on what it really means to ‘bless the Lord’.²⁵ The tropes glossed the versicle’s intention, whereas the ornate melodies and polyphonic performances reflected the blessing’s joy.

In medieval monastic usage, it was customary to sing elaborate settings of the *Benedicamus Domino* at the end of the major Hours, especially Vespers and Lauds, when it was followed by one or several commemorations, and concluded with a second *Benedicamus Domino* and the community’s response *Deo gratias*.²⁶ In some secular churches, the *Benedicamus Domino* also replaced the *Ite missa est* in Masses that lacked the Gloria (such as those during Lent). In Cistercian monasteries, however, the *Benedicamus Domino* was never used at Mass: instead, the celebrant employed the closing salutation *Dominus vobiscum*, eliciting the response *Deo gratias* from the congregation.²⁷ Therefore, we can safely assume that *Hu*’s substantial repertory of *Benedicamus* settings was performed exclusively in the Divine Office.

Extant medieval musical and liturgical sources from Las Huelgas shed only partial light on the ritual actions performed in the Office around

the *Benedicamus Domino*. On the one hand, *Hu* transmits only the musical elaborations of the *Benedicamus* acclamation and its poetic tropes. On the other, the liturgical Customary of Las Huelgas compiled in the 14th century (Burgos, Biblioteca del Monasterio de Las Huelgas, Ms. 6) alludes to rituals connected with the *Benedicamus Domino* only in passing and in a rather unsystematic way.²⁸ For instance, it specifies the order in which commemorations are to be performed after the (first) *Benedicamus* acclamation:

on the [day of the] commemoration of Saint Peter, once the *Benedicamus* is said at Lauds, they must first commemorate Saint John and then Saint Peter.²⁹

In order to learn more about the full *Benedicamus* ritual, it is necessary to refer to the Cistercian *Ecclesiastica officia*.³⁰ The *Ecclesiastica officia* (hereafter *EO*) were the official regulations issued by the Order in the 12th century. They provided a general framework within which Cistercian monasteries could organize their liturgy—the Las Huelgas Customary was directly modelled on the *EO*. The Customary features a miscellaneous collection of literal translations from the Latin *EO* into the vernacular Castilian, complemented with additions, interpolations and important adaptations.³¹ Thus, while the Customary provides many details about local practices and customs, it lacks the systematic organization that characterizes the *EO* and therefore features some significant gaps.

The Cistercian *EO* gives a more complete, general picture of the *Benedicamus* ritual. The chapter on the Office of Lauds, for example, states that:

When the *ebdomadarius* [the ‘weekly’, an individual who was charged with weekly duties] begins the *Benedicamus Domino*, everyone will stand up; he will bow when he has said it. At other Hours they do not get up until after *Deo gratias*, except at Vespers. If it is a Sunday, they stand facing the altar until the blessing of the cooks is completed. If there is a commemoration, let them stand as far as *Oremus* and then let them rest on their misericords and not stand until *Deo gratias*.³²

From this description, we learn that the *Benedicamus Domino* was more than merely a short acclamation. On Sundays, the ritual involved blessings to individuals and to groups within the community, the cooks being the last group to be blessed.

The individual blessings were then followed by multiple commemoration antiphons and collects.³³ For example, if the celebration of the Invention of the Holy Cross fell on a Sunday, antiphons and collects from three other Offices—Martyrs, Dominica and Ascension—were to be sung after the *Benedicamus* ritual at both Lauds and Vespers.³⁴ While the description quoted above fails to mention explicitly a second *Benedicamus* acclamation, other Cistercian official texts confirm the repetition of the words ‘*Benedicamus Domino*’ after the commemorations, followed by the community’s final response ‘*Deo gratias*’.³⁵ Table 1 summarizes the *Benedicamus* section of Lauds and Vespers, according to the *EO* and other Cistercian texts.

The late 13th-century liturgist Guillelmus Durandus makes it clear that the twofold acclamation of the *Benedicamus Domino* was an important feature of Vespers and Lauds. After explaining the meaning of the first *Benedicamus* acclamation, he continues as follows:

After the suffrages [i.e. intercessory prayers, or commemorations], another prayer is said which signifies the mercy of God, which precedes and follows men in their good works. Also, this is said again: *Benedicamus Domino*, and *Deo gratias*, because just as the Lord greeted His disciples again after the Resurrection, He blessed them, and they, offering Him thanks, adored Him. So too, the presbyter, or another one, having said the prayer, says for a second time: *Benedicamus Domino*; and this must be understood as: whose members we are, and in whom we offer a blessing; and He also blesses.³⁶

The elaborate *Benedicamus* settings transmitted in *Hu* functioned as further interpolations within this ritual context. Thus, in the most solemn liturgical celebrations at Las Huelgas, the *Benedicamus* acclamation was turned into a liturgical moment of great intensity by performing blessings, poetic tropes and various forms of polyphony. Still, it remains unclear whether the tropes and polyphonic elaborations were performed on the first, the second or on both occurrences of the *Benedicamus* within the same service. Which of the two *Benedicamus* acclamations was meant to sound more solemn: the first one—on which the sisters stood up—or the second, which marked the end of the entire service? Contemporaneous European ordinals give different indications.³⁷ The liturgical Customary of

Table 1 Closing section of Vespers and Lauds according to Cistercian sources

Liturgical items		Ritual action
<i>Benedicamus Domino</i>		The <i>ebdomadarius</i> begins, everyone stands up. The <i>ebdomadarius</i> bows at the end.
Blessings (on Sundays)		The brothers stand facing the altar.
Commemoration	Antiphon	The brothers keep standing.
	Versicle	The brothers keep standing.
	<i>Oremus</i>	The brothers sit on the misericords.
	Collect	The brothers remain sitting on the misericords.
<i>Benedicamus Domino</i>		The brothers remain sitting on the misericords.
<i>Deo gratias</i>		The brothers stand up, respond 'Deo gratias', bow and leave the choir.

Las Huelgas, however, fails to make specific mention of any trope or polyphonic performance for the *Benedicamus Domino*, perhaps reflecting a certain flexibility in this liturgical moment, which was constantly adapted to celebrations of varying degrees of solemnity and public projection.

Singers

The question of who sang the polyphonic *Benedicamus* settings compiled in *Hu* is also far more intricate than it would seem at first glance. In medieval monastic practice, the *Benedicamus Domino* traditionally used to be sung by soloists—from two to six, according to different European sources—at the centre of the choir. Some ordinals even specify that the *Benedicamus* was to be sung by the same two soloists who earlier would have chanted the responsory at first Vespers, or who later would sing the Alleluia at Mass.³⁸ Unfortunately, the surviving sources from Las Huelgas do not provide any information in this respect, but we know that the abbey included a collegium of chaplains and clerics (including altar boys) who were often involved in the conventual liturgy of the nuns, as well as a group of male singers specializing in polyphonic performance.

Marginal annotations in *Hu* provide clear evidence that the royal nunnery counted on the service of singers referred to as 'cantores' in the Castilian vernacular.³⁹ These are not to be confused with the Latin 'cantor', the ecclesiastical dignitary also known as 'precentor' ('capiscor' in the Castilian vernacular). In 14th-century Castilian, the word 'cantores' referred to paid singers who served in cathedrals

and aristocratic chapels. We know the name of at least one singer who served at Las Huelgas in the 1340s: Johannes Roderici, the only scribe in *Hu* who left his name on marginal annotations. He was a user of the codex's motet and conductus fascicles, and made necessary corrections to ensure that the pieces were performable by his group of male *cantores*.⁴⁰ Furthermore, Roderici himself compiled one motet and a small collection of troped *Benedicamus* settings at the end of the codex.⁴¹

The archives of Las Huelgas preserve no records of payments or lists of names that shed further light on the structure and specific function of this group of male *cantores* in the 14th century. It is only from the 16th century that there survive contracts and endowment documents, which specify the duties to be fulfilled by the musical chapel of 'instrumentalists and *cantores* of the Royal Monastery' on the most solemn, public celebrations, as well as the quieter conventual Hours.⁴² For instance, an endowment document issued in 1578 by Abbess Francisca Manrique stipulates that the *cantores* were required to sing:

a *villancico* at Vespers of Our Lady of the Assumption and, on the said feast-day of Our Lady, when the convent returns and enters the choir from the procession that transits through the cloister, another *villancico* And they shall sing one verse of the hymn at the convent's Vespers and Compline, as well as the Compline's *Salve [regina]*: all of that [shall be sung] polyphonically.⁴³

The musical adornment of the Divine Office in general had obviously changed substantially by the 16th century, by which time the *Benedicamus*

Domino had lost its prominence as the most musically elaborate section of the Office. Nevertheless, the document provides important clues about the way professional singers were involved in the conventual liturgy at Las Huelgas. If we assume that this practice had its roots in the late Middle Ages, it seems possible that, instead of *villancicos*, the 14th-century *cantores* performed motets and conductus at Vespers, and, instead of one verse of the hymn, they sang the *Benedicamus Domino* polyphonically.

The presence of specialized *cantores* at Las Huelgas does not indicate that the nuns themselves were unskilled or unwilling performers. On the contrary, the 14th-century chronicles and Customary of Las Huelgas show the extent to which the nuns were active as liturgical singers. It was the nuns, and not the clerics, who officiated at royal ceremonies such as coronation Masses, replacing the *cantores* of the royal chapel in certain parts of the sung liturgy.⁴⁴ While this is an indication of the higher status of the nuns' liturgical singing, cooperation between nuns and clerics was also constant at Las Huelgas. The Customary, compiled for and by the nuns themselves, distinguishes two possible ways of involvement for the nuns in the liturgy of the Mass. Depending on the occasion, they could either 'officiate' (sing) a Mass held by the clerics, or even 'celebrate' a Mass on their own, without the intervention of any priest—as surprising as it may now sound, the Las Huelgas Customary unequivocally states that the abbess could act as a celebrant and 'say Mass.'⁴⁵

The nun singers of Las Huelgas were equally active in the liturgy of the Divine Office. The Customary includes constant references to the *domadaria* (the female *ebdomadarius*) and the *cantora* (or *cantrix*, in Latin), while it rarely mentions any cleric or male singer in connection with the Office. Most likely this is the case because, since the Office includes no Sacrifice, the nuns were always the Office's liturgical leaders, and therefore there was no need to clarify a distribution between nuns and clerics, as occurred with the Mass. This, however, does not exclude the possibility that the clerics could participate in the conventual Office by singing specific verses.⁴⁶

Tellingly, the only reference to polyphonic performance in the entire Customary occurs in a chapter specifically addressed to the nuns: 'and on the first Sunday of Advent, they sing in three parts.'⁴⁷ If the

nuns performed three-part polyphony at Vespers and Lauds, there is little doubt that it would be the *Benedicamus Domino*—especially on a Sunday, when the *Benedicamus* ritual was extended with blessings by the abbess. In any case, the Las Huelgas Customary definitely suggests that polyphonic performances were not limited solely to the most lavish celebrations, but also formed part of the nuns' conventual liturgy even during Advent, when the services of paid *cantores* may not have been employed.

If both the nuns and the male *cantores* of Las Huelgas performed polyphony, did the two groups share the same *Benedicamus* repertory that is transmitted in *Hu*? The notion that clerics and nuns shared the same books is not unprecedented. Lori Kruckenberg reports various cases where men and women shared the singing duties of the Mass in 13th-century France and Germany: at Metz Cathedral, the ritual included the passing of a troper from the hands of the clerics to the hands of the nuns.⁴⁸ At Las Huelgas, both the nuns and the clerics had access to the space where books were stored.⁴⁹ While the identity of *Hu*'s main scribe remains unknown, the fact that the manuscript was used by male *cantores* did not exclude its potential use also by the nuns and *Hu* in fact survived to this day in the monastic library of Las Huelgas precisely because it belonged to the community.

Conclusion

The substantial provision of *Benedicamus* settings in *Hu* shows the importance of this versicle within the liturgy of the Divine Office at Las Huelgas. As noted, *Hu* contains by far the largest and most varied surviving collection of *Benedicamus Domino* settings compiled in the 14th century: a heterogeneous repertory characterized by a wide range of musical styles and textures of varying degrees of complexity. The *Benedicamus Domino* was indeed a complex ritual, which could potentially involve various forms of cooperation between nuns, clerics and male singers specializing in polyphonic performance. The twofold occurrence of the *Benedicamus* acclamation within the same service (before and after the commemorations) may have left room for multiple possible combinations of liturgical actors and musical performances, the ritual being constantly adapted according to the

degree of solemnity of the celebration and the availability of specialized singers.

The joyful character of the blessing ritual seems also to have been an invitation to add further musical delights to the liturgy. While the *Benedicamus Domino* is the only versicle of the Divine Office that is set polyphonically in *Hu*, it was by no means the only polyphony performed in the Office. Perhaps not coincidentally, the conductus fascicle in *Hu* opens with a long, untroped *Benedicamus* organum triplum (fols.129r–131r)—the most extensive *Benedicamus* setting in the entire codex. This seems to indicate the potential function of the *Benedicamus Domino* as a ritual framework for further paraliturgical performances. The polyphonic conductus that follow this opening *Benedicamus* organum are very closely connected thematically to the liturgy of the Office, often paraphrasing or drawing from Marian antiphons and hymns.⁵⁰ Such pieces could perfectly serve as musical interludes—analogueous to the 16th century *villancicos* discussed above—framed by *Benedicamus Domino* acclamations.

The *Benedicamus Domino* exhorted not only the monastic community, but also the congregation of faithful who attended the Office, to bless the Lord. The social outreach of the Las Huelgas conventual liturgy needs to be understood in relation to the abbey's political background. As its complex structure attests, Las Huelgas was much more than just a nunnery. Along with the cathedrals of Burgos, Toledo and Seville, the abbey played a central role within the Castilian court's network of memorial and ceremonial places. Because it housed the mausoleum of the legendary king

Alfonso VIII (d.1214), Las Huelgas became the court's favourite site at which to dub knights and perform coronation ceremonies throughout the late Middle Ages. As a major stage for the exhibition of power and for political propaganda, the nunnery had significant public exposure. The abbey church opened its doors to citizens and pilgrims, not only on the anniversaries of the royal persons interred there, but also on the most signalled feast-days of the liturgical calendar. Public attendance was even promoted through the offering of indulgences to the faithful who attended the festivities of St Mary and other commemorations at Las Huelgas.⁵¹

Like the spectacular Mudéjar plasterwork that covered the cloister's vaults, the polyphonic music that adorned the Divine Office was meant not only to delight the nuns, but also to impress the visitors who attended the most solemn services.⁵² Complex polyphony was perceived as a luxurious ornament of the church, most notably because of the specialized skills required to perform it. Johannes Roderici himself commented in marginal annotations on the beauty of the motets and conductus compiled in *Hu*, while warning his fellow *cantores* about the complexity and difficulty of some of these pieces. Or rather, he imagined what the pieces would say, could they speak: 'good am I, but the *cantores* doubt me and they still sing me incorrectly', or 'I am very beautiful, but not everyone knows how to sing me.'⁵³ This is testament to the extravagance and ambition with which the liturgy at Las Huelgas was adorned, a sheer delight in singing that is especially evident on the joyful occasion of the *Benedicamus Domino*.

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The production of this article was supported by the European Research Council in the context of the projects 'BENEDICAMUS: Musical and Poetic Creativity for a Unique Moment in the Western Christian Liturgy, c.1000–1500', Grant no.864174) and MALMECC (Music and Late Medieval European Court Cultures, Grant no.669190). With special thanks to Manon Louvriot.

¹ Roderici Ximenii de Rada *Historia de rebus Hispanie sive Historia gothica*, ed. J. F. Valverde (Turnhout, 1987), 7.23, p.255; Rodrigo Jiménez de Rada, *Historia de los hechos de España*, trans. J. F. Valverde (Madrid, 1989), p.303.

² These ideas are fully developed in D. Catalunya, 'A monastic court? Social space, courtly culture, and ceremonial practice at the royal nunnery of Las Huelgas', in

The networked court, ed. K. Kügle (London, forthcoming).

³ See *Documentación del monasterio de Las Huelgas de Burgos (1231–1262)*, ed. L. Garrido (Burgos, 1985), p.xv. See also D. Catalunya, ‘A female-voice ceremonial from medieval Castile’, in *Female-voice song in the Middle Ages*, ed. A. K. Grau and L. Colton (Leiden, 2022), pp.68–90.

⁴ For further bibliographic references on the culture of luxury and the intersection between court culture and monasticism at Las Huelgas, see Catalunya, ‘A monastic court?’; J. C. Ruiz Souza, ‘Las telas ricas en la arquitectura’, *Anales de historia del arte*, xxiv (2014), pp.497–516; *Vestiduras ricas: el monasterio de Las Huelgas y su época*, ed. J. Y. Luaces and M. Mancini (Madrid, 2005); P. Blessing, ‘Weaving on the wall: architecture and textiles at the monastery of Las Huelgas in Burgos’, *Studies in Iconography*, xl (2019), pp.137–82.

⁵ For a basic bibliography and editions of *Hu*, see H. Anglès, *El códex musical de Las Huelgas*, 3 vols. (Barcelona, 1931); *The Las Huelgas manuscript*, 2 vols., ed. G. A. Anderson, *Corpus Mensurabilis Musicae* 79 (Neuhausen-Stuttgart, 1982); *El Códice de Las Huelgas*, ed. J. C. Asensio Palacios (Madrid, 2001); N. Bell, *The Las Huelgas music codex: a companion study to the facsimile* (Madrid, 2004); D. Catalunya, ‘Music, space and ritual in medieval Castile, 1221–1350’ (PhD diss., University of Würzburg, 2016).

⁶ Nonetheless, many conductus and motets in *Hu* paraphrase or quote hymns, antiphons and responsories for the Office. See the manuscript’s inventory in Bell, *The Las Huelgas music codex*, and the critical apparatus in Asensio, *El Códice de Las Huelgas*.

⁷ The interest in sequences may be a local preference, as suggested by the survival of the substantial sequentiary from Burgos, Archivo de la Catedral, códice 61 fragmento 2, with concordances in *Hu*. See C. J. Gutiérrez, ‘El Prosario-Tropario con polifonía de San Esteban de Burgos’, *Studi Musiali*, ix/2 (2018), pp.247–332.

⁸ A. W. Robertson, “Benedicamus Domino”: the unwritten tradition’, *Journal of the American Musicological Society*, xlii/1 (1988), pp.1–62.

⁹ Noted by Bell in *The Las Huelgas music codex*, p.46.

¹⁰ Concordances in *F*, fol.65r; Wolfenbüttel, Herzog August Bibliothek, Cod. Guelf. 628 Helmst (*W*₁), fol.17r; and Wolfenbüttel, Herzog August Bibliothek, Cod. Guelf. 1099 Helmst (*W*₂), fol.47r.

¹¹ Franco of Cologne uses the term ‘punctus organicus’ to describe the practice of performing unmeasured passages at the end of sections in measured discant (*Franconis de Colonia, Ars Cantus Mensurabilis*, ed. G. Reaney and A. Gilles, *Corpus Scriptorum de Musica* 18 ([Rome], 1974), p.75). Although those in *Hu* are measured flourishes, the term seems appropriated to describe these kinds of organal passages, as they are set over single *puncta* rather than tenor melodies.

¹² See also Bell’s comments in *The Las Huelgas music codex*, p.117.

¹³ Rhythmic interpretation has been omitted in these transcriptions to facilitate comparison. As noted by Nicolas Bell, the notation of this piece in *Hu* ‘neither is entirely devoid of rhythmic implication, but neither has precise modal or metrical significance’. Bell, *The Las Huelgas music codex*, p.119.

¹⁴ See, for example, the *Benedicamus Qui nos fecit ex nihilo* on fol.23r, or the untroped *Benedicamus* on fols.25v–26r.

¹⁵ See further examples in A. Scarcez, *Liturgie et musique à l’abbaye cistercienne Notre-Dame de la Fille-Dieu* (Fribourg, 2015), and M. Gómez Muntané, ‘Deux nouveaux fragments polyphoniques antérieurs à l’Ars nova dans un manuscrit du monastère de Santa Maria de Vallbona’, in *Aspects de la musique liturgique au Moyen Age*, ed. C. Meyer (Paris, 1991), pp.177–90.

¹⁶ Noted by Bell in *The Las Huelgas music codex*, p.46.

¹⁷ Noted by Bell in *The Las Huelgas music codex*, p.59.

¹⁸ Noted by Bell in *The Las Huelgas music codex*, p.60.

¹⁹ On the origins and tradition of this piece, see A. Planchart, ‘The flower’s children’, *Journal of Musicological Research*, xxii/4 (2003), pp.303–48, and C. A. Bradley, ‘Contrafacta and transcribed motets: vernacular influences on Latin motets and clausulae in the Florence manuscript’, *Early Music History*, xxxii (2013), pp.1–70.

²⁰ See Asensio, *El códice de Las Huelgas*, p.580 no.33, and p.591 no.100.

²¹ Bell, *The Las Huelgas music codex*, p.49.

²² Pieces on fols.156r, 164v, 165r and 168r.

²³ For a summarized account of the chronology of the *Ars Nova* practice and further bibliography, see D. Catalunya, ‘Insights into the chronology and reception of Philippe de Vitry’s *Ars nova* theory: revisiting the mensural treatise of Barcelona Cathedral’, *Early Music*, xlii/3 (2018), pp.417–38.

²⁴ This was a very extended practice in the Middle Ages, which still prevails today. See *Consecrated phrases: a Latin theological dictionary*, ed. J. T. Bretzke (Collegeville, 2013), p.25.

²⁵ For theological and symbolic meaning of the *Benedicamus Domino* versicle, see Durandus’s *Rationale divinatorum officiorum*, v.9.62–3 in *Guillelmi Duranti, Rationale divinatorum officiorum*, ed. A. Davril and T. N. Thibodeau, 2 vols., *Corpus Christianorum, Continuatio Mediaevalis* 140 and 140A (Turnhout, 1995–8) and *Rationale V: Commentary on the Divine Office*, trans. T. M. Thibodeau (Turnhout, 2015).

²⁶ Here the term ‘commemoration’ refers to the insertion, within the liturgy of one celebration, of parts of another celebration of lower rank that could not be fully performed because of a coincidence of date. *Les Ecclesiastica officia cisterciens du XIIème siècle*, ed. D. Choisselet and P. Vernet (Reiningue, 1989), p.529. See also P. Morrisroe, ‘Commemoration (in liturgy)’, in *Catholic encyclopedia* (New York, 1908). Robertson, “Benedicamus Domino”, pp.6–7.

²⁷ *Ecclesiastica officia* 58.9, p.181. The same practice was observed at Las Huelgas (see Customary, ch.127, and D. Catalunya, ‘The customary of the royal convent of Las Huelgas of Burgos: female liturgy, female scribes’, *Medievalia*, xx/1 (2017), pp.91–160, at p.145).

²⁸ For a discussion of the Customary and a partial edition, see Catalunya, ‘The customary’. A full edition is in preparation by this author.

²⁹ ‘en la conmemoración de Sant Pedro, dicho el Benedicamus alas laudes, deuen faser conmemoración luego de Ssant Juan después de Sant Pedro’ (Customary, fol.67r). See Catalunya, ‘The customary’, p.142.

³⁰ *Les Ecclesiastica officia cistercien du XIIIème siècle*, ed. Choisselet and Vernet.

³¹ See the inventory of the Customary and its comparison with the *Ecclesiastica officia* in Catalunya, ‘The customary’, pp.114–17.

³² ‘Ebdomadario incipiente Benedicamus Domino, erigant se omnes. Quo dicto inclinet. Nam ad ceteras horas non surgant nisi post Deo gratias, excepto ad vespuras. Si dominica fuerit stent versis vultibus ad altare, donec benedictiones super cocos compleantur. Quod si fiet commemoratio. Stent ita usque ad Oremus, et tunc resideant super misericordias, nec surgant nisi post Deo gratias.’ *Ecclesiastica officia*, 69.16–20, pp.200–1.

³³ *Ecclesiastica officia*, 42.8, pp.134–5.

³⁴ *Ecclesiastica officia*, 46.2, pp.138–9.

³⁵ *Twelfth-century statutes from the Cistercian General Chapter: Latin text with English notes and commentary*, ed. C. Waddell (Cîteaux, 2002), p.35, and *The primitive Cistercian breviary (Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin, Preussischer Kulturbesitz, Ms. Lat. Oct. 402): with variants from the ‘Bernardine’ Cistercian breviary*, ed. C. Waddell (Fribourg, 2007), p.32.

³⁶ *Rationale*, v, ii, lxii, translation based on Thibodeau, p.114.

³⁷ For examples in other ordinals, see Robertson, ‘“Benedicamus domino”’, pp.6–7, and *Ceremonial according to*

the Roman Rite, ed. H. Dale (London, 1853), 5.23, p.134.

³⁸ Robertson, ‘“Benedicamus domino”’, p.7.

³⁹ Some of these annotations are quoted in the closing section of this article.

⁴⁰ For a complete analysis of Roderici’s corrections and marginal annotations, see Catalunya, ‘Music, space and ritual’, pp.99–104.

⁴¹ Roderici signed these pieces with the colophon ‘Johannes Roderici me fecit’. Most of them are reworkings and adaptations from other pieces. See Catalunya, ‘Music, space and ritual’, pp.99–104.

⁴² ‘clérigos capellanes músicos y cantores del Real Monasterio’; see M. P. Alonso Abad, ‘Mecenazgo musical en el Real Monasterio de las Huelgas de Burgos’, *Boletín de la Institución Fernán González*, ccxxx (2005), pp.149–76, at p.159.

⁴³ ‘la bispera de n[uest]ra señora de la asuncion a la calenda un villancico y el d[i]ho dia de n[uest]ra señora quando el conbento buelba y entre en el coro de la procesion que anda por el claustro otro villancico ... y an de cantar la d[ic]ha bispera a las completas del conbento un verso del himno ... y la salbe de las dhas completas todo ello en canto de organo.’ Alonso Abad, ‘Mecenazgo musical’, p.161.

⁴⁴ For further details on specific events, see Catalunya, ‘A female-voice ceremonial’.

⁴⁵ I argue that these were liturgical ceremonies which included all the chants and ritual actions of a Mass, except for the Eucharistic Sacrifice itself, which implied the consumption of pre-consecrated elements at Communion. See Catalunya, ‘A female-voice ceremonial’.

⁴⁶ As it occurred, for instance, in the Mandatum Office on Ash Wednesday. Customary, ch.86. Catalunya, ‘The customary’, pp.118 and 132.

⁴⁷ ‘E la primera dominica del Abiento cantan en tres boses.’ Customary, ch.108. Catalunya, ‘The customary’, p.140. See also Catalunya, ‘A female-voice ceremonial’, p.86.

⁴⁸ ‘unus de cantoribus debet accipere libellos qui dicuntur Tropier et debet eos dare monialibus ad cantandum Kyrie... Postea vero recedunt redditus libris.’ Metz Cathedral, *Liber ordinarius* (c.1240), *Inventio Stephani*. See also L. Kruckenberg, ‘Neumatizing the sequence: special performances of sequences in the central Middle Ages’, *Journal of American Musicological Society*, lix/2 (2006), pp.243–317.

⁴⁹ Cistercian monasteries typically had the *armarium* (the library) connected to the cloister, and the sacristy connected to the church’s transept (see the ‘plan type d’un monastère cistercien’ in *Les Ecclesiastica Officia*, ed. Choisselet and Vernet, p.23). In Las Huelgas, however, books and documents were stored, not in an independent room, but in the sacristy, a room that connected the clerics’ area with the nuns’ cloister. Today, an 18th-century altar blocks the entrance to the sacristy from the transept, but the medieval door is still visible from inside the room. See Catalunya, ‘Music, space and ritual’, p.216.

⁵⁰ See Asensio, *El código de las Huelgas*, pp.599–600 (critical apparatus nos.144–56).

⁵¹ For further details and bibliography, see Catalunya, ‘A female-voice ceremonial’.

⁵² Before the 16th century, pilgrims were even allowed to enter the church through the cloistered area (Catalunya, ‘A female-voice ceremonial’, p.73 n.19). For further bibliography on the cloister’s Mudéjar plasterwork, see Blessing, ‘Weaving on the wall’, pp.137–82.

⁵³ Roderici’s colophons speak in the voice of the musical pieces: ‘Bueno so yo, mas los cantores dubdan en mi e aún me yerran’ annotation of *Salve virgo / O dulcissima / [Aptatur]* (on fol.106v); ‘Yo so muy fermoso, mas non me saben todos cantar’, annotation for *Ydola dum subdola / [Et florebit]* (on fol.108r). For a complete edition and analysis of Roderici’s marginal annotations, see Catalunya, ‘Music, space and ritual’, p.101.

David Catalunya

***Benedicamus Domino*: delight in singing praise to God at Las Huelgas of Burgos**

The Las Huelgas Codex (*Hu*) features one of the most varied collections of medieval polyphony in Europe. It contains the repertory of Mass Ordinary settings, sequences, organa, conductus and motets that was in use at the royal nunnery of Las Huelgas in Burgos during the 13th and 14th centuries. While most of this repertory is known from other earlier sources, several of the numerous settings of the *Benedicamus Domino* in *Hu* are unique pieces that

reflect an apparently local practice. Closer inspection reveals, however, that nearly all of these ‘unique’ *Benedicamus* settings were created by borrowing and reworking musical material from other sections of the manuscript. This article considers the *Benedicamus Domino* settings as a musically cohesive sub-repertory in *Hu*, showcasing a rich array of reworking techniques. The article also considers the ritual function of the *Benedicamus Domino* within the liturgy of the royal convent, as well as the performance context and the distribution of singing duties between the nuns and the clerics of the monastery.

Keywords: *Benedicamus Domino*; Las Huelgas; Ars Antiqua; polyphony; liturgy; nuns; Cistercians